

Table continued.

Scientific name	SDR value ^b	Scientific name	SDR value ^b
<i>Cyperus haspan</i> L.	0.422	<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	0.185
<i>Hemarthria compressa</i> (L. f.) R. Br.	0.398	<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	0.151
<i>Phyllanthus virgatus</i> Forst. f.	0.378	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	0.132
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	0.336	<i>Mollugo pentaphylla</i> L.	0.112
<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	0.314	<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	0.112
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	0.228	<i>Scoparia dulcis</i> L.	0.112
<i>Eragrostis unioides</i> (Retz.) Nees ex Steud.	0.218	<i>Brachiaria murica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	0.092
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koel	0.197	<i>Euphorbia hypericifolia</i> L.	0.069

^aFloating leaf species. ^bMean ratio of relative density and relative frequency.

leaf weed. *Eriocaulon cinereum* showed a submerged life form in early rice growth stages.

For each species, we determined the summed dominance ratio (SDR)—the average of relative density plus relative

frequency. Seven locations were selected randomly and 10 quadrats in each location were temporarily positioned. Species were counted in 70 one-m² quadrats. On the basis of higher SDR value, *Eleocharis atropurpurea*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Rotala indica*, *Sagittaria guayanensis*, *Alternanthera sessilis*, and *Sphenoclea zeylanica* were the most commonly occurring weeds. ■

Water management

Irrigation methods for rice in tropical Australia

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Water is the largest single cost for irrigated dry seeded rice production in north Queensland, Australia. It accounts for about 40% of all variable costs. We evaluated increasing water-use efficiency by

- reducing water use while maintaining grain yield,
- increasing grain yield, while maintaining water use.

The experiment was conducted at Millaroo Research Station (19° 30' S, 147° 30' E) in 1989 dry season (winter). Traditional, intermittent irrigation to the 3-leaf stage, followed by permanent flood

(PF-3L), flooding at sowing (PF-S), flooding at panicle initiation (PF-PI), saturated soil culture (SSC), and intermittent irrigation (II) were compared. SSC is a technique recently developed for soybean: plants are grown on 1.5-m raised beds with water maintained in the furrows between beds, some 10-15 cm below the bed surface. II plots were irrigated by raising the water table to the surface at 7-d intervals. Irrigation treatments were in 288-m² plots replicated three times. Rice cultivar Lemont was used.

Rice yields were 8-9 t/ha in all treatments except II, which yielded 5.4 t/ha (see table). PF-PI and SSC did not reduce grain yield significantly. However, water use of PF-PI (12.1 million liters/ha and SSC (9.4 million liters/ha) was significantly less (P < 0.01) than that of PF-3L (13.7 million liters/ha). Most importantly, water-use efficiency (grain yield per unit consumption of water) of SSC (0.84 t/million liters) was significantly higher than that of PF-3L (0.65 t/million liters).

Grain yield and water use of rice cultivar Lemont grown under 5 irrigation methods at Millaroo Research Station, North Queensland, 1989 dry season.^a

Irrigation treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use ^b (million liters/ha)	Water-use efficiency (t/million liters)	% water ^c saved
Flooding at sowing	9.3 a	14.0 a	0.66 b	0
Intermittent irrigation followed by permanent flood	8.8 ab	13.7 a	0.65 b	
Flooding at panicle initiation	8.4 ab	12.1 b	0.69 ab	12
Saturated soil culture	7.9 b	9.4 c	0.84 a	31
Intermittent irrigation	5.4 c	7.9 d	0.68 ab	42

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^bIncludes all irrigation plus rainfall. ^cSavings calculated in relation to PF - 3L.

SSC used up to 1/3 less water than the flooded treatments because evaporation from the saturated soil surface was significantly less than that from a free water surface throughout crop growth. It should be noted that the cultivar used was developed for flooded rice production. The possibility exists that cultivars with improved yield under saturated soil can be developed. ■

Evaluation of drain performance based on head loss fraction in rice-growing acid-saline tract of Kuttanad

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Irrigated rice is the main crop in the acid-saline tract (Kari soils) of Kuttanad in Kerala. Because field elevation (0.5 to 1.5 m below sea level) is much lower than that of the surrounding water bodies, field preparation involves forming a ring bund and draining from inside. Pregerminated seeds are sown into puddled soils both wet and dry seasons.

Soils are extremely acidic and contain toxic concentrations of Fe, Al, and organic products. Yields are very low (1.0-1.5 t/ha), even with 100% adoption of high-yielding varieties. The hydraulic gradient created by the higher elevation water bodies brings toxic salts up to the root zone.

To limit that upward movement of salts and other toxic products, we experimented